

UPLIFT – Urban PoLicy Innovation to address
inequality with and for Future generaTions

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1 Introduction

The implementation of Reflexive Policy Making (RPM), that is the social innovation tested in the framework of the UPLIFT project (Box 1), is grounded in intensive research work. Qualitative research informed the development of the project by investigating the drivers of young people's inequalities and mapping existing counteracting measures. More precisely, the research carried out in eight European cities and published in the Case Study Reports (Annex 1) applied the Capability Approach (CA) to capture the complex socio-economic environment around young people and recommend possible topics for RPM. The eight analysed cities are Amadora (Portugal), Amsterdam (The Netherlands), Barakaldo (Spain), Corby, (the UK), Chemnitz, (Germany), Pecs (Hungary), Sfantu Gheorghe (Romania) and Tallinn (Estonia). Table 1 provides a brief overview of the eight cities and their young population demographics.

Box1: A brief introduction to Reflexive Policy Making¹

The UPLIFT project developed the Reflexive Policy Making approach to explore how young people's voices can be put at the centre of the whole policy process. RPM is a social innovation process that fosters change in actors' relationships to bridge the gap between the "system world" of institutional stakeholders and the "life world" of priority groups.

The main objectives of RPM are

- to create a durable institutional framework that empowers priority groups;
- to enable civil society organizations and individuals with the necessary capability to affect the design or implementation of policies.

To test the potential of RPM, UPLIFT partners carried out four parallel policy co-creation processes involving both vulnerable young people and institutional stakeholders in four different locations across Europe – Barakaldo, Amsterdam, Sfantu Gheorghe, and Tallinn - each with a different focus – education, housing and NEET youth.

¹ Gentili, M., Hoekstra, J., 2021, [Updated Action Plans for the co-creation process Looking back and looking forward](#), [Deliverable 4.2 UPLIFT](#), European Union's Horizon 2020 - grant agreement No 870898; Gentili, M., Hoekstra, J., 2023, [Guidebook on co-creation and reflexive policy making](#), [Deliverable 4.8](#), UPLIFT, European Union's Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898

Table 1: An overview of the eight analysed cities²

	Amadora (2017)	Amsterdam (2017)	Barakaldo (2019)	Corby (2017)	Pecs (2016)	Sfantu Gheorghe (2019)	Tallinn (2018)	Chemnitz (2019)
Municipal population (% of national pop)	1,69%	4,9%	0,21%	0,11%	1,46%	0,29%	32,65%	0.30%
Metro population (% of national pop)	27,53%	14,35%	1,81%	/	2,5%	/	44,67%	/
% Young people in Municipality (15-29)	6,37%	4,17%	6,49%	5,78%	5,69%	6,93%	5.99%	10% (2020)
Youth pop dynamic (municipal level)	-15% (2007-2017)	+29% (2007-2017)	+14% (2008-2019)	/	-20% (2005-2016)	-45% (2007-2019)	-20% (2007-2018)	-7% (1985-2020)

Aimed at policymakers and practitioners who are willing to adapt the RPM approach to their context, the Transferability Report comparatively analyses the Case Study Reports to **identify common issues, and thus common opportunities for RPM, among European Cities** (Chapter 1). In addition, the Report looks at the UPLIFT experimentation with RPM in four European cities (Work Package 4) to **explore how the proposed policy-making approach resulted in innovative solutions to tackle the roots of young people’s inequalities**. Overall, the aim of the Transferability Report is to provide inputs and inspirational examples for practitioners in the field of employment, education and housing services who would like to transfer and adapt the RPM approach to their specific contexts.

The **first chapter** of the Transferability Report summarises that part of the UPLIFT case study research that focused on micro-level drivers of young people’s inequalities in European cities.

² Data gathered by the each Case Study Report. UPLIFT, n.d. *Research-policy*, UPLIFT, European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898 (website), www.uplift-youth.eu/research-policy/ (last access March 23, 2023).

With a comparative approach, it analyses the qualitative research based on the Capability approach carried out in eight European Cities and published in the Case Study Reports. Considering the education, employment, and housing field one by one, the chapter firstly looks at the resource space of young people. In other words, it investigates all formal rights (e.g. laws and regulations) and possibilities (e.g. subsidy schemes, programmes against social inequalities), that define opportunities in the educational, employment and housing system to live a meaningful and fulfilling life. Secondly, for each service domain, the chapter scrutinises the forms of access to these resources that are conditional on institutional, family, and individual characteristics. Using the CA wording, the research specifically looks at conversion factors, defined as the abilities of individuals to convert material aid and formal rights into valuable opportunities.³

The first chapter elaborates on the following research questions:

- How do governance models of the welfare systems differ among the seven localities? What is the role of national governments? What is the role of local governments (no power devolved, residual role, implementer, all power devolved)
- What are the inequalities emerged in outcomes of the analysed welfare system in terms of inequalities?
- What are the most relevant factors that hinder or enable young people to make full potential of the welfare system?
- What are the most common recommendations researchers in the eight analysed locations would propose for future Reflexive Policy Agendas?

Having analysed the resource space and the conversion factors of young people in European cities, the **second chapter** provides examples of RPM outcomes and their links to the identified common recommendations. The chapter builds on the Reflexive Policy Agenda resulted from the co-creation with young people in the four experimental cities of the UPLIFT project, namely [Amsterdam \(D4.4\)](#), [Barakaldo \(D 4.5\)](#), [Sfântu Gheorghe \(D4.6\)](#), and [Tallinn \(D4.7\)](#).

³ Kimhur, B. (2020) How to Apply the Capability Approach to Housing Policy? Concepts, *Theories and Challenges*, *Housing, Theory and Society*, 37(3): 257-277

2 The resource space of youngsters in eight European locations - a comparative analysis

2.1 Education

2.1.1 Welfare system

In all analysed cases, the principles of free and universal education are established by the respective national **legal frameworks**. For instance, the educational legal framework of the Basque Country states that public schools work toward an inclusive, “plural, bilingual, and democratic” public school system with its “compensatory of inequalities and with the suitable environment to integrate diversity”.⁴ Similarly, Portugal and the Netherlands enshrined the right to freedom of education in their constitution.⁵ Beyond similar principles associated with education in different legal frameworks, the analysis reveals common patterns in the governance and institutional structure in place to provide educational welfare services in the seven locations.

In most analysed cities, the educational system is highly centralised. In Romania, Portugal, Hungary, and Spain, national governments hold responsibility for needs evaluation, resource management, curricula standardisation, and performance monitoring. Even in Estonia, where local governments still manage and regulate some aspects of preschool childcare and primary schools, recent reforms steer toward the standardisation of curricula to tackle imbalances between Estonian and Russian language schools. In Germany, education, according to the constitution, is jointly in the hands of the state (Land), which is Saxony in the case of Chemnitz and the municipality of Chemnitz. The Saxon education system follows an educational standard rather than a nationwide framework.⁶ Only in the Netherlands, the national law guarantees a very high level of autonomy for schools.⁷ Moreover, both public and private

⁴ Erice, L., Icaran Díaz de Corcuera, U., Icaran, C., 2023, [Case study report Barakaldo Functional Urban Area](#), deliverable 3.2, UPLIFT, European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898

⁵ Perista, P., Brázia, A., Teixeira, A., 2023 [Case study report Amadora Functional Urban Area](#), Deliverable 3.2, UPLIFT, European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898; Gentili, M., Hoekstra, J., 2023, [Case study report Amsterdam Functional Urban Area](#), 3.2, UPLIFT, European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898

⁶ Knorr-Siedow, T. 2022. [Urban Report - Chemnitz](#), 2.2 UPLIFT European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898

⁷ Gentili, M., Hoekstra, J., 2023, [Case study report Amsterdam Functional Urban Area](#), 3.2, UPLIFT, European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898

schools receive equal funding from the state. In the other analysed locations, local governments and schools have a **residual role** with no formal competencies and low resources. Therefore, **families, NGOs, and religious institutions** became important actors to absorb the disparate educational needs and flatten emerging inequalities. In Amadora, or Sfântu Gheorghe, and Barakaldo, the qualitative research mapped an emerging movement of civil society actors that collaboratively implement tailored-made policies to tackle inequalities. Among the interviewed experts and youths in Pécs, the perception is that civil society organisations independently assumed the equaliser role of public welfare.

Beyond the lack of adaptability to the local needs of a centralised and standardised governance model, the analysis highlighted two common institutional rules of education systems that might affect the resource space for young people. The first rule regards the **choice of the school location**. In Tallinn, Pécs, and Amsterdam, freedom of education is also reflected in the free choice of parents to choose the location of the school for their children (even if the schools in the school district has the obligation to take the children living nearby if they apply). Whereas, in Romania, where Sfântu Gheorghe is located, a recent educational reform abolished free location choice to prevent school segregation. In Chemnitz, primary schools are located within reachable distance by public transport, contributing to a formal freedom of choice in education.

2.1.2 Outcome

Using quantitative comparative parameters such as the drop-out rate, the case study reports describe divergent situations of the eight locations compared to the corresponding national average (Table 2). Barakaldo, Amadora, and Tallinn present slightly lower drop-out rates compared to their national average. Conversely, In the region of Sfântu Gheorghe drop-out rate stands at 27.8% compared to the national average of 15,3% and one of the highest rates among EU members of 15.3% (2018). Similarly, Pécs (the NUTS2 region where it is located) has higher drop-out rates than the national average.

Table 1: Early leavers by country and city

Early leavers from education and training		Early leavers from education and training	
Portugal	12,6% (2017)	Hungary	11,8% (2019)
Amadora	10,8% (2017)	Pécs	17,3% (2019)
The Netherlands	/	Romania	15,3% (2019)
Amsterdam	/	Sfântu Gheorghe	27.8% (2019)

Spain Barakaldo	17,3% (2018) 8,8% (2018)	Estonia Tallinn	11,3% (2018) 9,8% (2018)
England Corby	4.2% (2017) /	Germany Chemnitz	/ 11,2% (2019)

The qualitative research shows how lower performances and higher drop-out rates are amplified by housing segregation and persistent ethnic and racial discrimination. In Sfântu Gheorghe, where parents cannot have free choice over school locations, there are large differences between high schools. In three schools, the exam passing rate was 90%, while in another one was 17.6%. Students from segregated areas most often do not even start or do not finish high school. Even in educational systems in which parents can freely decide on school location, schooling segregation seems to be highly influenced by **housing segregation, ethnicity and the migration background of families**. In Tallinn, data on school attendance, and educational achievements reveal inequalities between Estonians and Estonian-Russians. The mismatch between the language skills obtained in Russian language schools and the required skills to enter later standardised higher grades leads to higher drop-outs rate among Russian-language students. In Pécs, the average drop-out rate is 17%, while the same rate among the Roma population is 62.7% (2021). Inequalities in drop-out rates are further reinforced by spatial segregation. In Amsterdam, the effect of early tracking and of the rigid division between vocational and other types of schools is reinforced by the higher share of residents with migration background who more often experience language barriers and discrimination from teachers. Even though the national school system supports vulnerable young people by the “system of supporting schools”, the efficiency of reaching out to those who have physical disabilities and social inabilities is not sufficient.

2.1.3 Conversion factors

Institutional factors:

- Education systems often do **not consider cross-domain influences**. A common issue both in locations with and without free parental choice of school location, a factor that amplifies educational inequalities is the influence of **housing segregation**. In Pécs and Tallinn, schooling and housing segregation are depicted as mutually reinforcing phenomena. In Amadora, it was found that youth in segregated housing situations are more likely to enter the vocational education path.
- Centralization of resource management and standardisation of curricula often **treat young people as a homogeneous group**. Schools lack the resources to implement tailored-made curricula. Experts from Pécs denounced the lack of resources, namely

educational capacities and financial investments for schools to adequately address specific needs and particular vulnerabilities. Experts in Barakaldo and in Pécs highlighted the lack of resources for individualised attention to specific vulnerabilities.

- Educational services **rarely provide guidance or orientation programmes to students**. This often leads to **scarce awareness** among young people about the possibilities they can have access to. In the case of Barakaldo, only 15% of the interviewed young people were able to name the existing institutions which provide educational services in the city. In Chemnitz municipal youth work provides counselling and support services not by the job centre but social institutions, which seemed to be particularly helpful especially for those students lacking family support.
- **Persistent ethnic and racial discrimination** encountered during the educational path. In Amadora, situations of discrimination and different treatment from teachers were pointed out as existing factors among interviewed youths. Teachers' discrimination becomes even more important when teachers have agency over students' educational choices. In Amsterdam, for example, the 2014-2015 reform of the tracking system prioritised teachers' assessment over the national standardised test for the selection of schooling paths. This represents additional risks in cases of biases and discrimination from teachers.

Family factors:

- **Language difficulties** of people with a **migration background** reinforce inequalities caused by the rigid separation of curricula and by an early tracking system (see the case of Amsterdam and Tallinn).
- **Family's social and economic capital along with parents' own educational experiences** engender strong educational **path dependency**. Given the lack of schools' resources, experts from all eight locations reported that families' economic resources, networking capacities and supportive attitudes become increasingly important in absorbing educational difficulties. Moreover, previous experiences of the family (parents or siblings) with the educational system highly affect the value given by the youths to education and thus their willingness to achieve higher grades.
- Functioning of the family strongly influences school outcome. In homes where children experience violence or absence of parents, this insecurity creates emotional burden on children, which negatively influences coping with life management including school tasks. For instance, in Chemnitz when psychologists intervene, they aim to involve the families and start a dialogue with them to prevent early failure of the student's education carrier.

2.2 Employment

2.2.1 Welfare system

Employment services and job market policies in all the analysed eight cities are centrally orchestrated by national governments. However, as opposed to the education system, in several cases, the analysis reveals a tendency towards stronger **cooperation between multiple levels of government**. In the case of the Basque Country, for instance, all three levels of government, namely the Basque Government, the Provincial Council, and local administrations, share responsibilities to provide different employment services. The Basque Government proposes a strategic, legislative, and regulatory framework for the entire region. Whereas local administrations implement and adapt top-down strategies to the specific local context. Also in Estonia, while the national level strategically designs employment policies, local municipalities deal with their adaptation and implementation. In Chemnitz the Ministry for Labour and Social Affairs is linked closely to labour issues. Policies are developed in a cooperation of employers, trade-unions, and civil society, mediated by the federal ministry.

In all the cases, the research identified similar active and passive labour market policies. All the analysed **passive measures**, which provide direct economic benefits, are governed at the national level. Estonia manages an unemployment insurance fund. Similarly, The Basque Country grants the Income Guarantee Programme that adds to the Minimum Living Income provided by the Spanish government. Among the analysed welfare systems, only in Romania passive economic support is provided specifically targeted to youth (between 16 and 24 years old) not in education, employment, or training (NEETs). The Ministry of Labour and Social Justice through the National Agency for Employment manages the Unemployment Insurance Budget targeting two hundred thousand young NEETS.

Passive measures are often coupled with **active employment services**. The Romanian Unemployment Insurance Budget is coupled with programmes that integrate young people into the job market such as apprenticeships or internships supported by the European Social Fund. Identified active measures range from tax facilitation or **recruitment grants** to companies hiring recent graduates (see the cases of Sfântu Gheorghe and Barakaldo) or **training and orientation programmes** (see for example the case of Barakaldo, Tallinn, or Sfântu Gheorghe).

The governance of **active measures** is not as homogeneous as it was described for passive policies. In Amadora, for instance, there are four Offices for Professional Integration that are run either by local administrative bodies (such as Juntas de Freguesias), or by NGOs. Civil society organisations in Amadora also directly collaborate with schools to deliver programmes to help young people integrate the labour market. Community associations together with schools help young people with writing their resumé or their motivation letters or practising

formal interviews. Similarly, in Pécs, several church-led initiatives or NGOs fill what interviewed experts interpreted as an institutional gap left by authorities such as the Employment Office. An inspiring collaborative practice between stakeholders was found in Barakaldo. Here, through the Territorial Dialogue Forum, the Basque Country Government together with multiple local administrations and key social actors implemented relief measures (food, economic aid or internet service) on the most vulnerable groups (e.g. housekeepers, caregivers, sex workers) to tackle their exclusion from other public programmes. In Chemnitz, the Federal Employment Agency and the Chamber of Industry and Commerce offer work or apprenticeship for job seekers. School leavers are supported by school social workers, youth-employment centres offering information, personal consultancy, access to youth employment projects.

2.2.2 Outcome

Unemployment, job precariousness and polarisation, and discrimination disparately affect young people in accessing the job market.

Unemployment does not largely diverge from the national level (Table 3). Only Amsterdam and Amadora experienced higher levels of unemployment than the national ones. However, it should be noted that young people are often the most unemployed group together with women and people with a migration background. In Tallinn, for instance, when looking at the 15-24 age group, the unemployment rate was 9.4% while the average unemployment rate is 4.4% (2018). Similarly, in the region of Sfântu Gheorghe, the youth unemployment rate (15-29) stands at 30% compared to the average regional 4.4%. Similarly, the share of **temporary or part-time contracts** is another aspect of the job market that disproportionately affects youths. In Barakaldo, for instance, 90% of new contracts are temporary or part-time. In Tallinn, despite the strong economic situation, the share of young people in precarious jobs increased from 5.7% in 2007 to 11.6% in 2018 in the age group 15-24.

The level of unemployment and the contract conditions also mirror **disparities in sector development** among cities. While the economy of Sfântu Gheorghe is still industry-based - the main economic activity is concentrated around clothing and food processing - Barakaldo, Amadora, Pécs, Tallinn, and Amsterdam represent different degrees of success in their transition to a service-based economy. Barakaldo and Amadora, two municipalities located on the outskirts of metropolitan areas, focused on the service sector as a driver of growth. However, the type of employment they have created remains unstable and low-skilled. Conversely, core metropolitan municipalities such as Tallinn and Amsterdam represent more advanced service-based economies. They attract workers from their metropolitan areas and from abroad by offering high-skilled jobs which remain at times inaccessible to local vulnerable populations.

In parallel to regional divergences in sector development, UPLIFT’s research reveals a robust **polarisation of the labour markets**. The share of both high-skilled, well-paid and low-skilled, less-paid positions is increasing, whereas average jobs are declining. This polarisation assumes a geographical dimension in metropolitan areas. In the labour market in Barakaldo and Amadora, located on the outskirts of Bilbao and Lisbon, low-skilled jobs are increasing. Whereas Amsterdam and Tallinn attract higher-skilled jobs. This phenomenon was not reported in Pécs, Sfântu Gheorghe and Chemnitz, smaller cities not integrated into a metropolitan area with a less diverse and polarised labour market.

Cities with weak economic potential or cities located on the outskirts of the metropolitan region with strong polarisation of the labour market often experience outmigration of young people. In Sfântu Gheorghe and Pécs, high-skilled young people often decide to migrate to others European Countries because they do not find suitable options locally. Similarly, in Barakaldo and Amadora, high-skilled youths preferred to move to other municipalities, especially to the core metropolitan area. Conversely, strong economic potentials such as Amsterdam and Tallinn became attractors for young people looking for highly skilled jobs from peripheral areas of the metropolitan area and from abroad.

Table 2: Cities’ economic status

	Amado- ra	Amster- dam	Barakal- do	Corby	Pecs	Sfântu	Tallinn	Chem- nitz
Part of Metro Area	Yes (peripher- al to Lisbon)	Yes (core)	Yes (peripher- al to Bilbao)	Yes (Peripher- al to London)	No	No	Yes (core)	No
Unemploy- ment (national)	8,9% (2017)	3,4% (2019)	13,7% (2018)	/	3,3% (2019)	5,4% (2018)	5,4% (2018)	5% (2019)
Unemploy- ment (local)	9,5% (2017, Metro Lisbon)	4,2% (2019)	12,9% (2019)	/	6,6% (2019, Baranya County)	5,3% (2018, Central region)	4,4% (2018)	5.5% (2019)

2.2.3 Conversion factors

Institutional factors:

- **Conditions** for benefiting from social and employment benefits are **too rigid compared to the fast-changing and precarious job market**. None of the interviewees from Sfântu Gheorghe benefited from social welfare because the qualifying conditions are too strict. In the Netherlands, people who benefit from social welfare tend not to accept even poorly paid or temporary jobs, in order not to lose their benefits.
- **Access rules** to social benefits and employment measures **fail to prioritise** the most vulnerable and specifically **young people**. For instance, in the Netherlands, according to the recent Participatory Society reform, young people are not supposed to be on social benefits. They should be either in full-time work or in education. The Explorer Programme, which aimed at supporting young people in Barakaldo in developing innovative ideas, was criticised because it targeted only a certain kind of young person with stable economic conditions.
- While employment active measures often blend with education or training activities, **passive measures hardly take into consideration cross-domain impacts**. For instance, interviewees in Pécs stressed the impact of the childcare system on the employment choices of women. In Barakaldo and Pécs, the experience of interviewees made clear the effect of a good metropolitan or regional transport system on people's choices about job location. As it was for education services, housing concerns in Amadora were identified as important factors for employment choices.
- Young people **lack information and knowledge** about provided services because of the **lack of orientation measures**. Lack of knowledge often leads to **raising mistrust in institutions**. In Barakaldo, Pécs, and Sfântu Gheorghe, when asked about national or local employment measures, young interviewees were not able to list available services or active stakeholders on the field.
- **Young people face persistent ethnic and racial discrimination** in taking employment life choices. In Amsterdam, Amadora, Pécs, ethnic discrimination is perceived as an obstacle to a satisfactory work trajectory. Residing in social housing is further perceived as a stigma that limits life choices. Experiences of racial discrimination range from being rejected at job interviews, having one's nationality questioned, or being the only non-white person in their work environment. In Chemnitz bullying and discrimination is a very direct barrier to getting a job especially in the field of manual professions which in some cases had led to immense self-doubt. In some cases, labelling students as bad in school decreased their motivation to study and then to inquire for a good employment position.

Family factors:

- Individual and family social capital. Networking skills and broad social connections represent an occasion for young people to discover new opportunities and alternatives.
- Path dependency of family and individual cross-domains life choices. Almost all Case Study Reports underlined how previous family life choices (e.g. housing location, access to transport infrastructure) continue to affect young people on their path towards independence.

2.3 Housing

2.3.1 Welfare system

While the comparative analysis reveals a tendency towards centralization of educational and employment welfare services, the housing field follows a different direction. Among the analysed cities, the trend is toward the management of centralised policies in regional and local offices. In Estonia, Romania, and Hungary local governments already hold responsibility for the design and implementation of a range of housing policies. In Spain, housing is managed by national agencies distributed in the territory with a certain level of autonomy over the allocation of budget. In Portugal, recent decentralisation reforms are charging local administrations with the responsibility of designing and implementing social housing solutions. Overall, interviewed experts highlight that decentralisation may lead to less effective rather than more effective policies, as local governments have been charged with additional housing responsibilities for which they lack financial and knowledge capacities. Chemnitz falls into the same trend with devolving competences to the states in the reform of the federal system in 2006.

The research identified two parallel phenomena among the narrow range of housing policies, namely the **liberalisation trend** and the **mismatch between target and priority groups**. Mapped public measures often aim at liberalising the market and fostering home ownership. Consequently, they often do not target priority groups, among which are young people who are especially vulnerable to inequalities when entering the housing market for the first time. Saxony's (the state where Chemnitz is located) housing policy is clearly dedicated to follow market principles within the framework for market actors created by the Ministry of Regional Development, however the quality and quantity of public housing is historically strong in the location.

Measures devised to increase the **housing stock** often focus on raising the rate of **home ownership rather than supporting (social) tenants**. In Sfântu Gheorghe, for instance, the municipality assigns plots for young families to build houses. Thus, only young families who have enough economic capital are incentivised to invest in the housing market. Only in

Amadora, where the national constitution grants special protection to young people, the analysis mapped a nationally led programme to increase social housing stock specifically for young people. The “New Generation of Housing Policies” aims at increasing the social housing stock in Portugal from 2% to 5%.

Also, by regulating access to social housing, public policies often tend to deny priority to youths and to incentivise the private market. For example, in more than one city, branded social housing access mechanisms for youths largely favour families with children while forgetting the heterogeneity of the youth population. In Pécs, mechanisms to access social housing favour those with extremely low-income levels (currently approx. 150€/head). Over this income level, the access is based on a tendering process, which gives higher scores for higher incomes and more upfront costs offered for the renovation of the flat by the future tenant. In Amsterdam, a recent national reform adjusted the point system that determines whether a housing unit is eligible for the social or private renting market. Adding house value to the point system, several units previously rented as social housing in expensive locations - especially in the centre of Amsterdam - shifted to the private market.

Another measure that increases youth vulnerability in accessing housing rather than supporting their concerns is the regulation of contracts’ length. Both Amsterdam and Pécs have recently reformed their renting contract regulation. In both cases, temporary leases were introduced as regular contracts. In the Netherlands, the government introduced contracts lasting two to five years both for private and social youth housing and for student housing.⁸

2.3.2 Outcome

A comparative look at the housing sections of the case study reports highlights two common phenomena that foster inequalities in the housing sector and particularly affect the resource space of young people. The housing market is experiencing a **sharp increase in prices** while the **public housing offer is shrinking**.

All eight cities, except for Chemnitz, are experiencing a **rapid increase in housing prices**. Estonia and Hungary are the countries with the most significant increase in the real estate sector in Europe in the last decade.⁹ Amsterdam and Barakaldo are experiencing a strong polarisation of prices between the private market and the public sector. Experts argue that the

⁸ Gentili, M., Hoekstra, J., 2023, [Case study report Amsterdam Functional Urban Area](#), Deliverable 3.2, UPLIFT, European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898

⁹ Geróházi, É., Katona, N., Kollár, S.G., 2023, [Case study report Pécs Functional Urban Area](#), Deliverable 3.2, UPLIFT, European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898; Beilmann, M., Kährlik, A., Otstavel, S., Pastak, I., 2023, [Case study report Tallinn Functional Urban Area](#), Deliverable 3.2, UPLIFT, European Union’s Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898.

increase in housing prices is not only linked to liberal policies, nor does it depend solely on a supply and demand logic. It is also linked to the attractiveness of the economic or educational potential of the city. For instance, in Pécs, housing prices are strongly driven by university students. In Amsterdam, prices are influenced by tourism, commuters, and financial investments. Young people who enter for the first time the housing market and have on average a lower income, are particularly affected by the increase in prices. In Chemnitz access to affordable housing is relatively easy for young first home-seekers as the supply and demand is quite equalised thanks to the low market pressure and the German rent regulation and the rent subsidy measures. Thanks to transfers of stock between the municipal housing company to welfare organisations or self-organisations of young people provide housing successfully for vulnerable young people to housing. However due to the Covid-19 and the current energy crisis, increasing share of low-income households in Chemnitz are facing with financial difficulties (called energy-poverty).

The impact of increasing housing prices is amplified by the **shortage of public housing**. Liberal policies, coupled with political shifts in the last forty years in some of the analysed cities, resulted in a domination of home ownership over the rental market. In Romania, the housing ownership rate is 95%. Similarly, in Estonia, it stands at 80%. Only Amsterdam is an outlier - among the analysed cities - with a homeownership rate of 30.8%. Parallel to the rise of the homeownership rate, cities experience a contraction of the public housing stock. Due to privatisation policies, public housing in Estonia shrank from 61% of the housing stock in 1992 to 4% in 2000. Public housing units in Amadora and Pécs represent respectively 2.8% and 5.5% of the housing stock. The shrinkage of the public housing stock coupled with higher private market prices causes an increase in pressure on social housing. Amadora is the fifth city in Portugal for the number of families in housing needs. In Amadora, the 3.9% of families - 2839 families in total- are signed in the waiting list as eligible for social housing.¹⁰

In addition to not being able to cover the housing need of priority groups due to the limited number of units, social housing in most analysed cities represent a risk for **spatial segregation**. More precisely, in all eight analysed cities experts identified a phenomenon of concentration of poverty. In Sfântu Gheorghe, the local administration owns only 137 social housing units that are all clustered together in three peripheral segregated areas. In Amadora, there are 2098 social housing dwellings, 73.7% of which are located in three large agglomerations where displaced people from self-constructed dwellings were moved. In

¹⁰ Perista, P., Brázia, A., Teixeira, A., 2023 Case study report Amadora Functional Urban Area, deliverable 3.2, UPLIFT, European Union's Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898.

Amsterdam, the recent social housing point system reform made it easier for units in economically low-value estates to enter the social sector.

2.3.3 Conversion Factors

Institutional factor:

- **Access rules are too restrictive and do not prioritize the most vulnerable categories.** As it was observed in the welfare paragraph, in Sfântu Gheorghe a housing policy for youths targeted only married couples favouring them when they have children.
- When housing policies target youths, they do **not account for the heterogeneity** of this target group. In Barakaldo, for instance, there are several programmes that implement the constitutional right for housing. However, they do not differentiate between vulnerabilities that differently affect youths.
- **Lack of orientation measures** leads to a **lack of awareness** among youths and eventually to a **lack of trust in institutions**. As already observed for employment and education services, interviewed young people are scarcely aware of public housing policies. Moreover, most of the time lack of knowledge of individual rights and potential benefits is combined with a lack of trust in institutions. In Amsterdam, interviewees perceive obtaining a social rental dwelling as a stroke of luck. While in many German cities digitalisation of housing services excludes vulnerable households, in Chemnitz reaching out and informing households via phone and personally in the office ensures low-threshold access to housing services.
- **Persistent discrimination.** The analysis identifies structural ethnic discrimination against the Roma community in accessing the private rental market (see the case of Sfântu Gheorghe and Pécs).

Family and individual factors:

- **Family economic capital** is key to entering the housing market. Several interviewees in different cities refer to the economic capital of the family as the only way for young people to escape vulnerability to accessing housing.
- **Family social capital** is key to escaping vulnerability in both public and private markets. Previous family experiences in the social housing sector are often perceived as a benefit to being able to navigate bureaucratic hurdles. When it comes to entering the private market, family networks and community ties are key to finding available solutions.
- **Individual networking and adaptation skills.** Peer networking seems to be preferred to institutional mechanisms to enter the housing sector. Due to the precariousness of housing contracts, networking abilities remain important among former young people.

Moreover, adaptability is perceived as an important factor since most young people tackle the increase in prices by sharing an apartment with friends or unknown flatmates.

2.4 Cross-domain conversion factors

Institutional factors:

- Education, employment, and housing welfare services **often work in silos preventing cross-domain influences**. Except for the provision of training opportunities to address employment issues, the mapped welfare services hardly account for the influence of multiple policy domains on the success of a specific service. Employment services rarely take into account the efficiency of regional or metropolitan transport systems as an enabler or barrier for achieving a valuable and fulfilling life. Similarly, housing solutions and access rules to social housing rarely consider the complex socio-economic dimensions of being in housing need. Education life choices often reproduce family employment and housing inequalities.
- In both analysed services, **access rules are often too rigid** compared to the fast changes in the socio-economic context.
- Even when targeting young people, employment, housing, and education measures often **underestimate the heterogeneity of this age group**. Thus, they do not tackle inequalities issues of the most priority groups. The gap between policy reach and priority groups is often explained by interviewed experts by a **missing ex-ante evaluation step in the policy cycle**.
- Employment, education, and housing services **fall short in communication, dissemination, and orientation**. Most interviewed young people could not refer to existing supportive measures or to public agencies active in the provision of welfare services.
- Lack of awareness of young people regarding existing employment, education, and housing services, as well as the perception of the mismatch between priority groups and policy reach are often linked by interviewees to a lack of trust in institutions. Young people often perceive access to public services as a matter of luck.
- Discrimination (either in the streets, or institutionalised by schools, public offices, work places, landlords) against certain groups of people e.g. ethnicity, origin, nationality, migration background, gender, LGBTQ and so on is a barrier in all domains.

Individual and family factors:

- **Language difficulties** of young people with a **migration background** are often perceived as factors that amplify inequalities in life choices in all domains.

- **Family economic capital** is perceived as a key determinant to achieving a meaningful and fulfilling life.
- Family and individual **social and knowledge capital** along with networking capacities are considered important factors to escape vulnerability in all analysed domains.

2.5 Common emerging topics for a Reflexive Policy Agenda

Reflexive Policy Making processes require an approachable more or less specific topic to work on, which can originate from 3 major sources: 1) Top down 2) Research-based 3) Moderated discussions. In the UPLIFT project in all 4 implementer locations and in four other locations a research was implemented to address potential topics for a Reflexive Policy Making process. Down in Table 4, the main recommendations for feasible policy changes or ideas for new services, that can be fine-tuned in the framework of RPM can be found as the results of the analysis of the qualitative research: interviews with young people in the frame of the capability approach. While different locations are differing from many aspects in terms of economical potentials, national and local welfare systems, the arising topics turned to be rather similar.

Table 3: Recommendations based on the main outcomes of the research for a Local Reflexive Policy Agenda

	Cross-domain	Education	Employment	Housing
Amadora	Engage families and interested stakeholders in building a strong supportive network for vulnerable young people	Supportive and strong role model network is needed for compensating for lacking family support, urge to start working early and inadequate studying conditions. Promotion of school success and preventing school dropout	Improve information stream of a wide range of jobs towards priority groups (Strengthen orientation programmes) to prevent skill mismatches and enable them to enter the labour market through better quality jobs.	Improve information stream towards priority groups (Strengthen orientation programmes) for enabling vulnerable young people to access adequate and affordable housing in the primer housing sector.
Amsterdam	Improve information stream towards priority groups (Strengthen orientation programmes) Engage families and interested stakeholders in building a strong supportive network Co-creation of service access rules	Improve information stream towards priority groups (Strengthen orientation programmes) with promoting through new partnering associations and online tools. Also enhancing the role of secondary schools as allies in improving knowledge of current youth policy is important. This could be further developed by training teachers to be more supportive and sensitive to vulnerable students.	Co-creation on regulation to make it more flexible and attuned to the current job market in order to make municipal programs (e.g., ALMPs) more accessible and competitive with informal networks.	Co-creation of transitory solutions with the establishment of a permanent round table on youth and student housing.

	Cross-domain	Education	Employment	Housing
Barakaldo	<p>Improve information stream towards priority groups, strengthen communication activities and channels to bridging through online channels, formal resources available in all domains and real opportunities for young people.</p> <p>Offering counselling and advice services by institutions in a holistic way</p>	<p>Promoting participating in educational programs enhances trust in institutions and enables young people to access opportunities through formal and informal channels.</p> <p>Capacity buildings in schools are important.</p>	<p>Holistic and individualised guidance is needed for young people both in their personal and professional life.</p>	
Chemnitz		<p>Motivate and inform transparently young people together with their parents to find their best possible educational pathway</p> <p>Provide orientation and services for smooth transition from education to employment</p> <p>Cooperative (non-competitive) relationships between educational actors (school psychologists, youth social workers) for empowerment approached (rather than care) for early intervention</p>	<p>Strengthen access VET and professional work to meet the needs of the local job market and the skillset and wishes of young people</p> <p>Equal access to the private job market for all regardless of gender, ethnicity etc.</p>	<p>Community building through free leisure facilities for more free time activities in large housing estates</p> <p>Co-creation of safe spaces in case of bullying, attack</p>

	Cross-domain	Education	Employment	Housing
Corby	<p>Transparency about rules, information in all sectors to enable individuals for informed decision making</p>	<p>Providing transparent information to allow young people to make informed decisions of their educational path.</p> <p>Engage families and interested stakeholders in building a strong supportive network as early intervention to a successful educational journey.</p>	<p>Bridge the gap between labour market needs, employment and education services</p> <p>Co-creation of guidance on career opportunities to be the most prepared with the adequate skills to the chosen employment pathway.</p> <p>Co-creation of local employment services to meet the needs of young people</p>	<p>Advice and guidance to make rules to access to local housing opportunities transparent and simple</p> <p>Co-creation of service access rules around affordable renting and regulations.</p>
Pécs	<p>Wide cooperation between all actors to cover precisely the needs of the target group, enabling transparent information flow between institutions and the beneficiaries</p> <p>Transitory solutions are needed between educational possibilities, between education and employment and in the different segments of the housing market</p>	<p>Promote equally all educational forms through orientation programs to bridge the mental gap between different forms of education to make it equally accessible for all social groups</p> <p>Easy transitory solution between different educational positions</p> <p>Early intervention through involving families into service provision to prevent</p>	<p>Bridge the gap between labour market needs, employment and education services through cooperations between institutions and between institutions and families</p> <p>Transparency of opportunities should be available for all</p> <p>Retraining opportunities for transitioning young people to match the labour market needs</p>	<p>Co-creation of services provided or channel resources to champion individualised care especially for preventive reasons (indebtedness)</p> <p>Co-creation of service access rules and target in a wide cooperation of local actors and the target group to make the local housing system transparent and efficient</p> <p>Co-creation of transitory solutions to ensure interoperability between the</p>

	Cross-domain	Education	Employment	Housing
		<p>early leaving, school drop-out and unsuccessful educational journey</p> <p>Training for teachers and educational staff (psychologists, social workers, youth workers etc.) for preparing them to be sensitive to the students' individual needs</p>	<p>Early intervention regarding vulnerable residents to systematically engage them to prevent especially long-term unemployment</p>	<p>segments of the housing sector according to individual need</p>
Sfantu Gheorghe	<p>Engage families and interested stakeholders in building a strong supportive network</p>	<p>Developing a reliable relationship between teachers, administrators and parents, to enable parents to better support the school career of students.</p> <p>Collaboration for strengthening the links between NGOs and schools to develop as cheap as possible after-school programs for students and make service provision more effectively targeted.</p> <p>Trainings for teachers in conflict management, group dynamics, inclusion and bullying.</p> <p>Strengthen peer-to-peer relationships through mentorship volunteering</p>	<p>Improve information stream of the offers of the Local Employment Agency and the municipality towards priority groups (Strengthen orientation programmes)</p> <p>Co-creation of services provided or channel resources to champion individualised care which also attract people to stay in the local labour market.</p> <p>Bridge the gap between labour market needs, employment and education services through developing job qualification courses</p>	<p>Improve information stream towards priority groups (Strengthen orientation programmes)</p> <p>Apply concrete measures for the most marginalised groups of the city</p> <p>Series of community conversation to enhance mutual understanding of different social groups in different housing positions in the city.</p> <p>Co-creation of service access rules e.g., regarding debt management and the regulating rents also initiate programs</p>

	Cross-domain	Education	Employment	Housing
		programs and developing networking skills to contribute to successful school attendance	Strengthen peer-to-peer relationships and networking opportunities	for energy efficient renovations especially for low-income families.
Tallinn	Individualised one-to-one career counselling	<p>Develop early prevention of vulnerabilities through individualised care for learning difficulties, mental and physical difficulties, bullying and training teachers, school psychologists and other specialists to counteract with early school leaving.</p> <p>Improve information stream on potential suitable professions towards priority groups either by the school or by the Youth Work sector</p> <p>Co-creation of services provided or channel resources to champion individualised care</p>	<p>Improve information stream towards priority groups with individualised one to one career counselling sessions especially through the Youth Work sector.</p> <p>Co-creation of a transitory solution for Russian-speaking young people to integrate into Estonian language speakers.</p>	Co-creation of access rules to social housing especially focusing on the affordability of independent housing for youth in general without re-stigmatisation.

Building on the analysed conversion factors, all Case Study Reports propose a set of topics to be included in possible Reflexive Policy Agendas. Table 4 above summarises what partners in the eight locations recommended. As it is visible from this table, the most common horizontal topics for RPA can be grouped as:

Recommendation 1: Co-create tailor-made, personalised services, access rules and transitory solutions in a holistic manner.

Recommendation 2: Improve the flow of information towards priority groups on available services and orientation programmes.

Recommendation 3: Make early interventions and involve the families of vulnerable young people in service provision and create spaces for community building and networking

3 Inspirations to implement Reflexive Policy Agendas

The current chapter aims to provide inspiration to those policy actors who intend to work out feasible local solutions to improve the position of vulnerable young people by presenting evidence on how the most common horizontal policy issues (revealed in chapter 1.5) that all the European urban locations are suffering from, can be handled by local interventions. These suggested interventions were piloted in four locations of UPLIFT (Amsterdam, Barakaldo, Sfântu-Gheorghe and Tallinn) through the Reflexive Policy Making Process (see Box 1), thus we find it useful to highlight their **transferability potential** to any other urban locations of Europe.

Below we recall the most common horizontal issues of policy making and implementation that were revealed as a deficit in all eight urban locations of UPLIFT where detailed research was carried out.

Recommendation 1: Co-create tailor-made, personalised services, access rules and transitory solutions in a holistic manner.

Recommendation 2: Improve the flow of information towards priority groups on available services and orientation programmes.

Recommendation 3: Make early interventions and involve the families of vulnerable young people in service provision and create spaces for community building and networking

3.1 Amsterdam¹¹

In Amsterdam, the co-creation process has been focused mainly on the housing situation of young people. The overall goal of the working group has been in fact to propose suggestions and recommendations for new and existing policies that can improve the vulnerable housing conditions of youngsters in the city.

The co-creation process has led to the development of a set of recommendations targeting housing policies and specific policy tools. Five out of the six priorities identified are part of broad and holistic measures for housing policies, therefore contributing to Recommendation 1, focussing on the provision of multiple, different and inclusive housing opportunities for a larger part of the local community, taking action on three different levels: legislative, spatial and social measures.

¹¹ Gentili, M., Hoekstra, J., 2023, Co-creation with young people in Amsterdam- Research approach and Reflexive Policy Agenda, Deliverable 4.4, UPLIFT, European Union's Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898.

More specifically, one of the first priorities for the Youth Board would be **to see the Municipality engaged in the provision of Temporary Rental Contracts** to those students with an approaching deadline for their student contracts. This would be functional to support them in the transition to the broader housing market, without being forced to move back to their parents' home or have to relocate outside of the city.

Together with this, the working group underlines **the need for changes in the regulatory framework for co-housing initiatives and housing cooperatives**. Easing and providing better information regarding those opportunities would provide youngsters with cheaper and more inclusive housing, fostering the sharing of accommodation and an intergenerational mix. Regarding this, the second sprint of the co-creation process has resulted in the development of a proposal for an **"inclusive communal youth housing concept"**, which the housing association Lieven de Key aims to integrate into projects for housing redevelopment foreseen for the Amsterdam Nieuw West area. Priority 6 underlines the need to call on higher levels of government, mostly at the national level, to address those measures that are hindering and limiting housing opportunities for youngsters and elderly people.

In a multi-disciplinary and integrative approach, this should come with the provision of better, connected and larger housing facilities on the edges of the city. Furthermore, the Youth Board suggests **keeping track and making use of the many vacant buildings around the city**, engaging the local community in the proposal of activities or housing initiatives to bring those places back to life.

Moreover, the RPA presented by the Amsterdam working group underlines the need to provide better and more complete information to young people looking for affordable and adequate housing in the city. In doing this, they suggest the **development of a Virtual Platform** that could collect and summarise relevant information for those navigating the challenging housing market. This would then contribute to improving the flow of information towards priority target groups (Recommendation 2). In this regard, representatives of the Youth Board and !WOON (an NGO working in the field of housing) got in contact with the municipality to explore opportunities to integrate such a platform into existing plans developed for the Amsterdam South East Area. Despite the idea not being successful, the initiative has been functional in raising awareness about the need to provide clear and objective information regarding housing conditions and regulations for the local community.

The co-creation process has already led to some results with a number of suggestions developed by the Youth Board included in the integrated draft version of the new housing vision of the Municipality of Amsterdam. This has led to more attention towards youngsters' issues when it comes to housing conditions and the research for accommodation. With the hope that it will be structurally embedded in the housing policy system, the Housing

Association and !WOON have recently decided to continue their work with the Youth Board, with a fourth co-creation sprint focusing on collaborative housing, which started in January 2023.

3.2 Barakaldo¹²

The co-creation process in Barakaldo, Spain has led to the identification of four main priorities, mainly addressing and contributing to the development of a holistic and inclusive approach, fostering multi-level governance and collaboration with neighbouring municipalities, but also supporting youngsters in their emancipation process.

In fact, what is underlined by the RPA developed by the working group of Barakaldo, is the need to **collect and analyse the data regarding the different modalities of households** residing in Barakaldo, in order to get a fuller and more detailed picture of the adjustments needed to satisfy youth's housing needs and priorities. Together with this, another priority identified through the co-creation process is that of **generating synergies and collaboration with other municipalities** aiming to better coordinate actions targeting youth's emancipation.

In addition to that, two other points for policy improvements have been developed, addressing the need to better and ease the flow of information and resources available for youth's emancipation and independence. Gazte Bulegoa, ERETZA, together with Social Action and Housing engages in the **development of tools providing better, centralised and simplified access to information**. This would be part of a larger scheme that sees the set-up of an **"Emancipation School" for young people in Barakaldo**. Through the organisation of workshops, the trainers aim to help youngsters deal with practical matters, such as paying their bills and DIY activities.

The Barakaldo team has identified two main recommendations that might be helpful in the construction, implementation and follow-up of a Reflexive Policy Agenda, namely to:

- Make sure that the suggestions and points raised by the youngsters are thoughtfully integrated into the priorities identified and in the final outcome of the process, which is the RPA.

¹²Erice, L., Díaz de Corcuera, I., 2023, Co-creation with young people in Barakaldo - Research approach and Reflexive Policy Agenda, Deliverable 4.5, UPLIFT, European Union's Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898.

- Visualise and concretize the priorities identified and develop coherent actions, commit stakeholders to deadlines and follow up the compliance of the commitments.

3.3 Sfântu-Gheorghe¹³

The co-creation process carried out in Sfântu Gheorghe resulted in a 6-point priority list and the overall vision of enhancing the access of vulnerable children and youngsters to quality education. Five of the six priority points precisely address recommendation no. 1 suggesting strengthening the policy feedback loop mechanisms to design services able to better answer territorial and personalised needs. Priority 1 calls for the **development of auxiliary school infrastructure**: dormitories, cafeterias, and transportation in order to fill the infrastructural gap between schools. Priority 3 highlights the need for getting the schools ready to handle school violence, including **more appropriate responses to bullying and discrimination**. Priority no. 4 advocates for **assuring additional aid to school staff** (supporting teachers, school mediators, developing teachers, logopaedists, and school counsellors) to better address the students' specific, or young people lacking family support. Priority 5 proposes to **initiate actions that help both pupils and teachers feel better in school** and thus enhance the learning and teaching process. Finally, priority 6 calls for better cooperation between institutions that are directly or indirectly connected to education and youngsters in order to get a better picture of the current status and of the possible development of education in Sfântu Gheorghe. Recommendation 3, namely the one proposing the engagement of families and the creation of spaces for networking and community building is addressed in the case of Sfântu Gheorghe by priority 2 which proposes to **strengthen the triangle of cooperation between school, parents, and students**. No priority points of the Reflexive Policy Agenda developed in Sfântu Gheorghe directly address recommendation 2 even though a lack of information about existing employment and housing services was revealed by the analysis.

Moving from prioritisation to implementation, two pilot projects are being implemented in the first semester of 2023 in Sfântu Gheorghe. One of the projects will involve conducting sensitivity workshops for educators who work with vulnerable youth (recommendation 1), while the other project will focus on building youth communities within schools (recommendation 3).

Inspired by the UPLIFT project, the **Municipality of Sfântu Gheorghe established a Youth Bureau in 2022**, led by the vice-mayor. The Youth Bureau conducted research among young

¹³ Suppedito Ltd., Sepsi Local Action Group Association, 2023, [Co-creation with young people in Sfântu Gheorghe - Research approach and Reflexive Policy Agenda](#), Deliverable 4.6, UPLIFT, European Union's Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898.

people aged 14-25 in the city and initiated programs to address identified issues. In 2023 and 2024, the Youth Bureau will expand its activities to other aspects of the Reflexive Policy Agenda related to youth communities. The Youth Bureau also aims to establish a Youth Parliament to enable young people to express their views and participate in municipal policy development (recommendation 3). Moreover, since Romania's National Recovery and Resilience Plan for 2023 and some Structural European Union Funds also focus on education, in line with recommendation 1 the municipal plan is **to transform two local marginalised schools into pilot schools where innovative educational methods and management styles will be tested.**

Even though the implementation phase in Sfântu Gheorghe only started a few months ago, partners in the field have already recognized a challenge in the turnover of young participants in the RPM process. Given that the current members who participated in the experimentation have completed high school, they may no longer be involved. It is thus crucial to plan the transfer of knowledge to establish new ownership of ideas. To overcome this issue, partners in Sfântu Gheorghe planned a transition phase. Before joining, new participants will have to attend a **preparatory camp** during which they will focus on personal development, knowledge transfer from the previous generation, and implementing short-term actions from the Reflexive Policy Agenda.

3.4 Tallinn¹⁴

Through a co-creation process, the Youth Board of Tallinn together with involved institutional stakeholders transformed punctually identified issues into opportunities for the improvement of educational, employment, and housing services. Overall, the proposed priorities address recommendation 1 and recommendation 2.

One point of the Reflexive Policy Agenda of Tallinn calls for innovative solutions to cover the gap between the delivered services and the needs of vulnerable young people (recommendation 1). All stakeholders agree on the schooling failure of timely detecting problems before students decide to drop out of their educational path. To tackle this problem, the Youth Board proposed to provide easily accessible training/study materials, programs, and **training to teachers and other specialists in schools on students' special needs and on school bullying.** Beyond advocating for service improvement, the Youth Board developed a guidance document to improve the provision of individualised services and to better coordinate these services (so that they are more in line with the needs and challenges of the

¹⁴ Kährnik, A., Kõiv, K., Paabort, H., 2023, Co-creation with young people in Tallinne - Research approach and Reflexive Policy Agenda, Deliverable 4.7, UPLIFT, European Union's Horizon 2020, funded under grant agreement No 870898.

NEETs). Also, an electronic tool has been developed based on this guidebook. The soft skills training programme for young people will be submitted to the Estonian Unemployment Insurance Fund, which is currently developing virtual training for young individuals who require guidance to kick-start their careers. Additionally, this initiative will be incorporated into the training program of the Association of Estonian Open Centres, which is seeking extra funding to execute it.

The second and third priorities identified by the team in Tallinn address recommendation 2, namely the need to improve the flow of information between institutions and priority groups and orientation services. Both pointing at employment and educational services, the Tallinn Case Study Report proposes **to increase awareness of young people about the existing services**. With a proactive approach to the analysed issue, the team developed an **online electronic platform called “Chat”** to improve access to services for young people – an outreach tool to enhance mobile youth work.

During the implementation of solutions, the team of stakeholders and young people in Tallinn encountered the following problems:

- **Limiting legal framework.** The activity of developing a ‘Chat’ (the virtual tool) has not been fully completed as a result of legal restrictions (GDPR).
- **Difficult engagement of young people.** Motivating young people to participate in meetings and co-creation activities was complicated.
- **Language barriers.** Although young people with a Russian background have often studied in an immersion class, their everyday communication has taken place in a predominantly Russian-speaking environment and therefore their ability to speak the local language (Estonian) is often low. Consequently, the language barrier has had some effect on their input at co-creation meetings.

4 Annex

Report	Responsible partner	N° of interviewees
Case study report, Amadora, Portugal	CESIS	46 interviewees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 current young (15-29 years old) • 20 former young (30-43 years old) • 6 experts
Case study report, Amsterdam, the Netherlands	TU Delft	48 interviewees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 current young (20-29 years old) • 20 former young (30-45 years old) • 8 experts
Case study Barakaldo, Spain	Orkestra, Deusto foundation	48 interviewees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 current young (18-29 years old) • 20 former young (30-42 years old) • 8 experts
Case study Chemnitz, Germany	UP19	63 interviewees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 21 experts • 22 current youth (16-25 years old) • 20 former young (30-43 years old)
Case study report, Corby, the UK	Young Foundation	47 interviewees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 current young (15-29 years old) • 20 former young (30-42 years old) • 7 experts
Case study report, Pécs, Hungary	Metropolitan Research Institute	62 interviewees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 current young (15-29 years old) • 20 former young (30-43 years old) • 22 experts
Case study report, Sfântu-Gheorghe, Romania	Suppedito SRL	48 interviewees <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18 current young (15-29 years old) • 22 former young (15-29 years old) • 8 experts

[Case study report, Tallinn, Estonia](#)

University of Tartu

48 interviewees

- 20 current young (15-29 years old)
- 20 former young (30-43 years old)
- 8 experts